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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, XIX
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This report is about tests and statistics for the solutions made from a set of 'provisional' 30-month Case History Files.

1. Provisional CHF:s

The 'real' 30-month CHF-generation uses new photometric reductions that have only recently been completed. In order not to be unduly delayed in the tests of the 30-month DS solutions, I made therefore a provisional CHF-generation, using an older (spring-93) photometric calibration, but otherwise with all recent data for attitudes, set zero-points and so on. With some unexpected practical difficulties, including time-differences up to 1 second(!) between (older) RGO-data and newer attitudes, 30-month CHF:s were generated for the selection of systems described in NDAC/LO/149. To save space and effort, however, only HIC-numbers 1-30000 were considered, giving finally 2794 'known doubles'(D), 3302 'suspected non-singles'(S), 251 'multiples'(M) and 1270 'bona-fide singles'(I).

2. Calibration solutions

The standard solution program SEEKDBL was then used on the (I)-CHF:s, which as expected gave mostly single-star solutions. Comparison with NDAC's sphere solution gave very encouraging results (see below), but with systematically deviating mean errors. As before (see NDAC/LO/145), the mean errors were brought closer by changing the empirical C_i/n_{scan} -terms in the covariances. Provisional values 12, 8 and 18 mas² in α, δ and π ; 24 and 14 (mas/yr)² in the proper motions, were thus derived.

Then the special version of STDDBL using only each 2:nd observation was used on the (D)-CHF:s. Two independent solutions are obtained for each system, and the differences between them can be compared with the solution mean errors. In this way, empirical magnitude-dependent correction-factors for the sigmas were derived, which came out rather similar to the corresponding relations for the 18-month solution. (In particular, the relations are somewhat different for 'absolute'(=position, proper motion and parallax for the primary) and for 'relative'(=relative position, proper motion and parallax, plus photometry) data. For comparison, I alternatively made the corrections depend on the normalized fit to the observations, $S_f (= \chi^2/\text{ndof})$. I had concluded long ago that a 'theoretical' $\sqrt{S_f}$ -multiplication of the mean errors was too pessimistic, because S_f includes effects of photometric errors and variability that do not directly influence the astrometry. The '2-sol' results showed now, however, very convincing increases of the observed deviations with S_f , which I tried to model again by different relations for 'absolute' and 'relative' data.

Naturally, I also tried to make a combined correction $\sigma = \sigma_o f_1(Hp) f_2(S_f)$, but because of correlations between Hp and S_f , this does not work. (A large f_1 gives a large offsetting f_2 , but neither is significant). If one had enough data, a detailed

function $f_c(Hp, S_f)$ might be derived empirically, but so far, it seems safer to calibrate the sigmas *either* as a function of magnitude, *or* as a function of S_f . The latter option seems preferable, and my present σ -calibration model is as follows:

1. In the DS solution programs, the raw covariances are augmented by the above C_i/n_{scan} -terms. This corrects approximately for the systematic attitude-errors which are highly correlated in FOVC:s along a similar scanning-direction. (The exact values for the C_i are rather uncertain, mainly because they are derived by comparison with sphere solution covariances that were themselves corrected rather ad hoc for this effect).
2. Then, the ‘absolute’ covariances are multiplied by $f_{\text{abs}}(S_f) = 0.40 + 0.50S_f$, and the relative ones by $f_{\text{rel}}(S_f) = 1.8\sqrt{S_f}$. In both cases, a cut-off is necessary for the largest S_f . This is not well-defined, but I make the corrections so far only for $S_f < 4$, keeping the factors at $f(4)$ beyond that.

This may seem very ad hoc, but the important point is that it *does* reproduce the ‘2-sol’ internal errors to within some 20% in most cases, with similarly small systematic trends with S_f or magnitude.

An ‘external’ test is again obtained by comparisons with the sphere solution for effective singles. Table 1 gives the absolute and normalized (divided by the sphere solution mean errors) differences with respect to NDAC’s sphere solution for the ‘bona-fide singles’, for three different magnitude-intervals. Also given are the mean covariance-ratios (DS(corr!)/sphere).

Table 1. Statistics for the differences between the DS- and sphere solution results for stars in different magnitude-intervals. The absolute differences are given in mas (mas/yr), while the normalized differences have been divided by the (sphere solution) σ . Simple means and standard deviations for the covariance-ratios are also given.

Parameter	Hp	n	Abs diff		Norm diff		cov(DS)/cov(sph)	
			mean	stddev	mean	stddev	mean	stddev
α	< 7	131	-.09(0.76)		-.07(0.76)		0.92(0.30)	
δ	< 7	131	-.07(0.62)		-.08(0.74)		0.94(0.28)	
π	< 7	131	-.00(0.81)		-.01(0.65)		0.89(0.18)	
μ_α	< 7	131	-.25(0.90)		-.19(0.63)		0.98(0.31)	
μ_δ	< 7	131	.31(0.76)		.31(0.71)		0.87(0.30)	
α	7-10	934	-.00(0.68)		.01(0.56)		0.90(0.25)	
δ	7-10	934	.02(0.60)		.02(0.59)		0.89(0.23)	
π	7-10	934	-.01(0.86)		-.01(0.56)		0.90(0.21)	
μ_α	7-10	934	-.09(0.96)		-.05(0.56)		0.93(0.27)	
μ_δ	7-10	934	.22(0.86)		.16(0.60)		0.84(0.23)	
α	> 10	98	.02(1.75)		-.01(0.76)		1.07(0.34)	
δ	> 10	98	.25(1.18)		.14(0.65)		1.08(0.31)	
π	> 10	98	.10(1.53)		.06(0.61)		1.09(0.34)	
μ_α	> 10	98	.26(2.26)		.09(0.72)		1.10(0.41)	
μ_δ	> 10	98	.30(1.89)		.14(0.71)		1.07(0.32)	

Although the number of solutions at the bright and faint ends are a bit small, the above figures show convincingly that true milliarcsec precision is now at hand. (Cf.

the similar Table 1 in NDAC/LO/145 to see the improvement from 18 to 30 months). Also, the covariance-ratios are not far from unity, although the DS covariances were calibrated mainly through '2-sol' experiments on double-star CHF:s.

3. Internal motions

A quite different 'external' test has been tried for the systems with known orbits. Francois Mignard has made available a set of computed relative positions *and* internal motions for known orbital systems at epoch 1991.5. Some 80-90 of these have good DS solutions, and one may compare both the relative positions and the motions with the computed ones.

For the relative positions, the agreement is at first sight unexpectedly poor. Even when all badly deviating objects are removed, the typical position error is some 50 mas, while the solution sigmas are more like a tenth of this. I have not checked the sources and quality of the orbital elements, but obviously there are many cases with systematic errors at the 0.1 arcsec level. In retrospect, this might however have been expected, as the orbits are often derived from visual observations with this kind of errors. It is clear, however, that almost all the observed deviations are due to the 'bad' orbits, and no useful information about the quality of the Hipparcos positions is obtained.

For the relative motions, the situation is much better. Even a 'bad' orbit is likely to show qualitatively and quantitatively the correct orbital motion. Accepting those orbits where the calculated position is offset from the observed one by less than 25% of the separation, I get a sample of 78 observed and calculated relative motions. In the α and δ directions, the mean differences are -0.2 and -0.4 mas/yr, with standard deviations 9.5 and 6.7. Dividing the differences by the DS solution sigmas, this gives normalized means +0.1 and -0.1, standard deviation 1.9 and 1.6. (This is a real result: normalized standard deviations around 5 is obtained by putting the calculated motions to zero). A normalized standard deviation close to unity can be obtained if one adds a 'model error sigma' of about 5 mas/yr in each coordinate. This seems quite reasonable, given the 50 mas errors in the positions over maybe 10-year baselines. (Trying to use only the highest-quality orbits gives no further information: with 5% position errors as the acceptance-limit, only 18 orbits remain).

The conclusion from this limited but powerful test is that the solutions for (linear) relative motion seem to be reliable. Only in rather few cases, however, is this motion significant, as may be seen from some simple statistics from the present solutions. Out of 3845 solutions, 59 give an unrealistically high relative motion (> 0.5 arcsec/yr), and are so far discarded (most of them seem to be poor solutions of large-separation/ large Δm pairs). Of the remaining 3786 solutions, 339 (9 %) have at least a 3σ relative motion, 118 (3%) a 5σ -one, and only 21 (0.5%) a 10σ relative motion. (Many of the latter are indeed among the known orbital pairs).

4. Spurious solutions

An important question is to what extent one may trust the 'new' solutions, where no a priori elements are known. From earlier simulations, it is clear that the number of spurious solutions should now be much smaller than before, but this has to be verified in some way. An obvious test is to run SEEKDBL (no a priori information) for a number of known doubles and see which systems are 'discovered' correctly. For this purpose, I use a SEEKDBL-run over the (D) CHF:s, with a limiting search-radius of

5.8 arcsec. One may look first at the results for doubles which really have smaller separation than this. In Table 2, I have defined a ‘good’ SEEKDBL sol to be one with all parameters within 3σ of the STDDBL-sol, while for a ‘grid-step’ solution only the relative separations differ, but with a difference within 0.2 arcsec of $1.2n$ arcsec. A (double-star) solution not fulfilling any of these criteria is ‘bad’, and SEEKDBL may also output a ‘single’ solution, or a ‘problem’-case (with no solution at all). These raw percentages show conclusively that most doubles with ‘reasonable’ Δm_{eff} will be discovered by SEEKDBL. For the largest Δm_{eff} , many of the differing solutions have a ‘grid-step’ error, while all other parameters come out correct, including the position, proper motion and parallax of the primary. (The ‘problem’-cases are mostly large-separation/equal-magnitude pairs where the normal route followed by SEEKDBL (sing solution for photocentre, then search for secondary) is non-optimal. Among the real suspects, such systems should be very rare).

Table 2. The percentages of ‘good’, ‘grid-step’, ‘bad’, ‘single’ and ‘problem’ solutions for a run of SEEKDBL on known doubles.

Δm_{eff}	good	grstp	bad	sing	probl
0-1	77	2	8	1	11
1-2	87	2	6	2	3
2-3	86	2	9	3	1
3.0-3.5	79	6	13	3	0
3.5-4.0	66	11	20	3	0
4.0-4.5	53	22	18	7	0
4.5-5.0	30	21	21	27	2

Another interesting test is obtained by running the ‘bona-fide singles’ (I-CHF:s) through SEEKDBL, with search-radii out to 5.2 arcsec. Out of 1269 solutions, 129 were classified as double, 1140 as single, with no ‘problem’-cases. This seemingly high number of ‘spurious’ double solutions can be very illustratively counted as function of Δm_{eff} . It then transpires that only 13 solutions have $\Delta m_{\text{eff}} < 4.0$. It is thus immediately clear that one gets an excess of spurious solutions with large Δm_{eff} , and that it is necessary to exclude the most difficult ones.

In an attempt to define the cut-off more rigorously, I study the Δm_{eff} -distributions for the above ‘bona-fide singles’, as compared with the one for the ‘suspected non-singles’ (S-CHF:s). The simple idea in Table 3 is to scale the number of (S)-solutions to the number of (I)-solutions, and to estimate thus an upper limit to the number of spurious solutions in the (S)-results. (It is an upper limit, because there may of course be some real doubles among the (I)-systems). The very encouraging result is that even at Δm_{eff} around 4.5, some half of the solutions found should be for real doubles, (although some of them may have bad parameters as found in Table 2 above).

From test such as these, one may give some statistical estimates about the fraction of trustworthy results at different Δm_{eff} , but it is not trivial to do it rigorously. So far, using the above tables as a guideline, I simply use $\Delta m_{\text{eff}} = 4.5$ as a practical cut-off. ‘New’ solutions with $\Delta m_{\text{eff}} > 4.5$ have more than a 50% chance of being spurious, and are therefore excluded.

Table 3. The distributions of Δm_{eff} for the double-star solutions from ‘susp’ (N(susp)) and ‘bona-fide single’ CHF:s (N(Spur)). N(SuSc) is N(Susp) scaled to the same number of attempted solutions (3297 vs 1297). The percentage of spurious solutions should not be greater than N(Spur)/N(SuSc).

Δm_{eff}	N(Susp)	N(SuSc)	N(Spur)	%(Spur)
<2.0	424	163	2	1
2.0-2.5	199	77	0	0
2.5-3.0	204	79	0	0
3.0-3.5	266	102	3	3
3.5-4.0	341	131	8	6
4.0-4.5	379	146	38	26
4.5-5.0	245	94	78	83

5. Multiples

The (known) multiples have long been neglected, mainly because there are so many unsolved problems for the doubles. Very slowly, however, some progress is made.

One of the main obstacles has always been the a priori data. The solution program for multiples needs relative positions within 0.1-0.2 arcsec in order to converge satisfactorily, as only the primary position is varied in a standard mesh-search. A major part of the effort thus has to go into creating an a priori file with positions (and magnitudes) for the individual components. This has turned out to be exceedingly difficult, partly because the Annex1 of the IC needs completion from other sources (Torino, WDS ...), partly because the ‘grouping principles’ are so hard to define, but mainly because there are so many different ‘layouts’ when there are more than two components to take care of. I have tried to define a general MULAPR-file that is read from the solution program, but the programs writing MULAPR from Annex1 and from the Torino-catalog still do not work satisfactorily.

As for the STDMUL solution-program, it was developed through simulations, and has not been updated since about december -91. I have been able to get it running, however, by adjusting some formats and adding the apriori-read from MULAPR. When the a priori data are correct, a solution is obtained, and there are in principle no reasons why most multiples should not get solved eventually. Much further work is needed for STDMUL, however, as it lacks all refinements added to STDDBL and SEEKDBL in the course of the ‘real’ reductions.

As an example of the present state of this process, I give in Table 4 the solutions (or non-solutions) obtained for the ‘multiple’ CHF:s with HIC 1-2700, by STDMUL and by SEEKDBL, to get an unbiased solution for any ‘dominating close double’ in the system. These runs are *very* preliminary, but it seems that when a double-star solution is all that can be obtained, this solution is often found both by SEEKDBL and STDMUL. When a triple solution is obtained by STDMUL, the SEEKDBL solution sometimes fails or is erroneous, which shows the importance to use a multiple-star solution if such a priori data are available.

Table 4. Solution results for ‘multiple’ CHF:s, as obtained by SEEKDBL and STDMUL. When no data are given, either no solution at all was obtained, or an ‘excluded’ one. (Thus, for several CHF’s, neither program gave a solution).

HIC	Hpr	SEEK		STDMUL			
		sep	dm	sep1	dm1	sep2	dm2
303							
365	6.19	5.34	4.03	5.34	4.05		
374	7.92			0.72	0.28	22.69	2.47
424							
461	8.31	0.12	1.24	0.12	1.25		
865	7.00	0.29	1.64	0.29	1.64		
1076	6.85	0.32	0.90				
1233	6.82	0.15	2.66				
1392							
1699	8.83	0.41	1.52				
1700	7.63	0.57	0.94				
1732	7.81	1.62	1.89	6.10	1.67		
1805	8.16	3.94	3.52				
2074	7.01	1.95	2.69	1.95	2.70		
2252	9.00	0.55	0.08	0.55	-0.10	7.77	3.93
2327	10.82	1.51	0.46	0.94	0.43	12.22	1.52
2328	9.83	1.01	0.56	1.01	0.56		
2414	7.98	0.11	0.41	0.26	3.08		
2460							
2509	8.42	5.53	3.26	6.65	3.06		
2533	8.89	2.59	2.51				
2543	7.27	2.84	3.48				
2573	7.13	3.79	4.48	3.81	5.22		
2642	7.77			0.63	0.66		

6. Conclusions

The main conclusion from the above tests is that the ‘real’ 30-month DS solutions (with the improved photometry) will probably be mostly well-behaved. Much of the calibrations and solution-optimizing has already been done with the preliminary data, and ‘routine’ STDDBL+SEEKDBL results will be available soon after the CHF:s are available.

Before the new CHF-derivation, it remains to select the stars to be included, which needs both the new photometry (Hp(AC)-Hp(DC) being a main detection-criterion for ‘suspects’), and an improved Torino-catalogue (with the WDS-data included). A list of ‘bad sphere-sol stars’ should also be used, because this may include some ‘curved photocentre’ astrometric binaries.

In parallel with the ‘standard’ reductions, a lot of work must be done improving the STDMUL-program, but it now seems this is fully feasible.